

Competencies of science teachers of private secondary schools in Bacoor City: A basis for faculty development program

Joel G. Matamis*

Medical Laboratory Science Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: jgmatamis@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Future successful science professionals depend largely on how well science teachers have trained and thought them. There is an immense need for competent teachers who teach and train students for quality education and consequently, to be a better person when they soon become professionals. This study is beneficial to the students because of the prospective positive changes among the teaching behaviors of their teachers which will assure them that their science teachers are competent and are adequately equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills especially in the field of science to help them develop personally and professionally and thus recipient of a quality education. This study focused on the competencies of science teachers in private secondary schools in Bacoor City in terms of planning and teaching materials; instructional strategies; communication skills and evaluation tools. The research used a descriptive approach, collecting information from science teachers and fourth-year students in ten private schools. Statistical tools such as frequency and percentage, weighted means, t-tests, and chi-square were used to compare how teachers and students perceived their skills and to see how teacher profile variables were connected to their competencies. Based on the salient findings of this study, science teachers were young, female dominated, and most of them were not enrolled in graduate studies. The study uncovered that science teachers are competent in the areas of planning and teaching materials, instructional strategies, communication skills and evaluation tools. It is also revealed that there is a significant difference in the perceptions of the students and science teachers in their competencies, as well as there is a significant relationship between the competencies of the science teachers to their years of experience in the teaching profession and forms of training attended.

Keywords: Competencies; Science teachers; Private secondary schools; Bacoor City; Faculty development program.

To cite this article:

Matamis, J. G. (2021). Competencies of science teachers of private secondary schools in Bacoor City: A basis for faculty development program. *SDCA Journal of Medical Technology*, 2, 9-15.

Introduction

Science education is seen as important for a national development, helping students gain the skills, values, and knowledge needed in a world that is becoming more science and technology focused. The competence of science teachers creates a big impact on how students learn, ask questions, and become future professionals. Hedges (2012) said that teachers do not just give information; they show how to think and engage with knowledge.

In the Philippines, private secondary schools are significant because they help increase the support of the public education system and offer different ways for students to learn (Termes et al., 2020). There is a strong need for effective teaching, especially in science, since it connects to the country's competitiveness and development (Vera Cruz et al., 2017). However, there are worries about how well teachers are prepared, their access to advanced studies, and how often they get training and support.

Teacher competence covers several areas, including understanding the subject, teaching methods, communication skills, and creating effective assessments. Studies show that teachers' qualifications, experience, and training make a big difference in how well they teach (Kyndt et al., 2016; Orchard & Winch, 2015; Roberto & Madrigal, 2018). In the Philippines, especially in private schools, there is not much research on what specific skills science teachers have. This is especially true in fast-growing areas like Bacoor in Cavite province.

Research on teacher competencies has shown that the quality of teachers is one of the most important factors that affect student achievement in school. Fitzsimons (1997) said that governance and competency standards directly affect how teachers practice professionally. Chan et al. (2014) pointed out the value of student perceptions in evaluating teacher effectiveness. Insteffjord and Munthe (2017) also said that teachers' attitudes and technological competencies can affect not just how well they teach, but also how interested students are in learning.

Internationally, studies on science education have shown that teachers play a key role in helping students develop skills like asking questions, thinking critically, and solving problems. Cheung & Phillipson (2008) discussed about teachers of gifted students in Hong Kong and found that subject-matter expertise, adaptability, and innovative instructional strategies are three core competencies that a teacher should have. Similar results have been found in Southeast Asia, where better teacher training has been associated with improved performance in science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) subjects (Mahmud et al., 2018; Suvarma & Kumano, 2019; Tan et al., 2018).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) requires teachers to continue professional development through the Enhanced Basic Education Act (RA 10533) and the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Law (RA 10912). But there are still problems with how this is carried out, especially in private schools. Teachers often have a lot to do and do not get much support from their schools for more education. Studies show that while many teachers have earned their professional licenses, there are still gaps in their advanced education, ongoing training, and access to new teaching tools (Abay & Morallo, 2019; Alegado, 2018; Alda et al., 2020).

This study aims to examine the skills of science teachers in private secondary schools in Bacoor City, as perceived by the teachers and students. It focuses on four areas: planning and teaching materials, instructional strategies, communication skills, and evaluation tools. It also looks at how these skills relate to teacher characteristics such as educational attainment, eligibility, teaching experience, and training. The results will help create a program for faculty members to improve their science teaching and learning in the local area.

It determines not just at what teachers earn about their own skills or competencies, but also how demographic variables such as age, years of service, and training are connected to their skill development. This matches the push for better, more tailored support for teachers that considers the specific needs of their schools and communities.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the students and the science teachers themselves in their competencies.
2. There is no significant relationship between the competencies of the science teachers to their profile variables.

Methodology

This study used a descriptive research design to evaluate the skills of science teachers in private secondary schools in Bacoor City. According to Mohajan (2020), a researcher can gather a lot of data, but this data alone cannot show that one variable causes another variable. Ten schools that offer secondary education took part in the study, and there were two groups of people who answered the questions: science teachers and fourth-year students.

To collect data, the researcher used structured questionnaires that checked four areas of teacher competence: (1) planning and teaching materials, (2) instructional strategies, (3) communication skills, and (4) evaluation tools. The questionnaire was checked by education experts and tested with a small group before it was distributed to the participants.

Different statistical treatments were used to analyze the data. This includes the following: frequency and percentages for demographic information, weighted mean for levels of competence, t-test for comparisons how teachers and students perceived about their skills, and a chi-square test to see if there was an association between teacher skills and their profile variables such as educational attainment, professional eligibility, years of teaching experience, and training.

The researcher made sure to follow ethical rules towards participants, such as asking permission from everyone who took part, keeping their information private, and ensuring that they understood what was being asked of them before they agreed to participate.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the respondents. Ten (10 or 66.7 percent) of the respondents are 20 to 29 years old and five (5 or 33.3 percent) of the respondents are 30 to 39 years old. Majority of the science teachers are female (8 or 53.3 percent), single (12 or 80 percent). Nine (9 or 60 percent) are bachelor's degree holders. Majority (11 or 73.3 percent) of them are Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) passers. Most (9 or 60 percent) of the science teachers have 1 to 5 years' experience in teaching profession and all of them (15 or 100 percent) have training along their job assignment. Seminar (13 or 86.7 percent) ranked first among the form of training and school (10 or 66.7 percent) in the level of training attended by the respondents.

Level of Competencies of the Science Teachers in Private Secondary Schools as perceived by themselves and the Fourth Year students in terms of:

Planning and Teaching Materials. Both respondents affirmed that science teachers are competent as evidenced by an overall weighted mean of 4.21 (science teachers) and 3.88 (students).

Instructional Strategies. An overall weighted mean of 4.15 for the science teachers' perception and 3.91 for students' perception indicates that the science teachers are competent.

Communication Skills. The science teachers are competent in communication skills as perceived by themselves and confirmed by the students as indicated by an overall weighted mean of 4.25 and 3.94 respectively.

Evaluation Tools. The science teachers perceived themselves competent with an overall weighted mean 4.16 in evaluation tools. This is affirmed by the students with an overall weighted mean of 3.83.

Significance of the difference in the perceptions of the students and the science teachers themselves as to planning and teaching materials; instructional strategies; communication skills; and evaluation tools. There is a significant difference in the perceptions of the science teachers (mean = 4.19, standard deviation = 0.04) and the students (mean = 3.89, standard deviation = 0.04) regarding the competencies of the science teachers based on the computed t 10.71, which is significant at 5 percent level.

Significant relationship between the level of competencies of the science teachers when grouped according to profile variables. There is no significant relationship between the competencies of the science teachers when grouped according to highest educational attainment, as evidenced by a computed chi-square value of 2.51, less than the tabular value of 9.35 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that science teachers can be competent regardless of the educational level attained. There is no significant relationship between the competencies of the science teachers when grouped according to professional eligibility, as indicated by computed chi-square value of 5.24, less than the tabular value of 12.59 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that the competencies of the science teachers have nothing to do with their professional eligibility.

There is a significant relationship between the competencies of the science teachers to the years of experience in the teaching profession, as evidenced by a computed chi-square value of 16.39, greater than the tabular value of 15.50 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies, the older the science teachers in the service the more competent they become. The form of training attended by the science teachers is significant to their competencies, as indicated by a computed chi-square value of 13.57, greater than the tabular value of 12.59 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. The result denotes that the more training attended by the science teachers the more competent they become.

There is no significant relationship between the level of training attended with the competencies of the science teachers, as evidenced by the computed value of the chi-square 6.07, less than that tabular value of 23.68 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, regardless of what level of training, if science teachers attend training these will make them competent. There is significant relationship between the competencies of the science teachers to the years of experience in the teaching profession, as evidenced by a computed chi-square value of 16.39, greater than the tabular value of 15.50 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the older the science teachers are in the service the more competent they become.

The form of training attended by the science teachers is significant to their competencies, as indicated by a computed chi-square value of 13.57, greater than the tabular value of 12.59 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. The result denotes that the more training attended by the science teachers the more competent they become. There is no significant relationship between the level of training attended with the competencies of the science teachers, as evidenced by the computed value of the chi-square 6.07, less than that tabular value of 23.68 at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, regardless of what level of training, if science teachers attend training these will make them competent.

The science teachers' competencies are significantly related to the years of experience in the teaching profession and form of training attended but not significantly related to highest educational attainment, professional eligibility and level of training. The researcher came up with a proposed faculty development program (see Appendix A) through a seminar training to further strengthen the competencies of science teachers and for them to become highly competent.

Conclusion

This study found that science teachers in private secondary schools in Bacoor City are mostly skilled in areas such as lesson planning, instructional strategies, communication, and evaluation. However, there is a significant difference between how both teachers and students perceive their competencies. Being competent is closely connected to how long a teacher has been teaching and what training they have taken, but not much to their education level or whether they have the proper qualifications. These results show that real-world experience and ongoing learning are more essential for teaching skills than just having formal degrees or licenses. Therefore, special training programs for private school teachers could really help improve the quality of science education.

Recommendations

The school should initiate a faculty development program to help teachers grow by offering training in new teaching methods, better communication skills, and understanding how to evaluate student learning. This program should follow a plan that connects different types of training and seminars. The school should also encourage and support teachers to enroll for master's or doctoral degrees. Instead of short discussions or interviews, the school should offer longer, structured training sessions that are connected to real classroom teaching. Science teachers must select appropriate assessment techniques and instruments for their instructional competencies and must modify activities. To further enhance students' critical and creative thinking, teachers should work together by observing each other, joining groups where they can share ideas, and doing research projects that help them improve their teaching. Future studies could also investigate other factors that affect school leadership, workload, and access to instructional resources.

References

- Abay, J. R., & Morallo, M. B. (2019). Gaps on quality teaching: Assessing teachers' needs towards the creation of a framework for an extension program on teachers' professional development. *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(3), 28-36. <https://www.ioer-imrj.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Gaps-on-Quality-Teaching-Assessing-Teachers%E2%80%99-Needs-Mayumi-B.-Morallo-Jemil-R.-Abay.pdf>
- Alegado, P. J. (2018). Breaking the barriers: Teacher leadership in the hearth of educational reform in the Philippines. *Bulgarian Journal of Science and Education Policy (BJSEP)*, 12(1), 15-30. <https://eprints.worc.ac.uk/13952/>
- Alda, R., Boholano, H., & Dayagbil, F. (2020). Teacher Education Institutions in the Philippines towards Education 4.0. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(8), 137-154. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.8.8>
- Chan, C. K., Luk, L. Y., & Zeng, M. (2014). Teachers' perceptions of student evaluations of teaching. *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 20(4), 275-289. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803611.2014.932698>
- Cheung, H. Y., & Phillipson, S. N. (2008). Teachers of gifted students in Hong Kong: Competencies and characteristics. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 17(2), 143-156. <https://www.ejournals.ph/article.php?id=3893>
- Fitzsimons, P. (1997). The Governance of teacher competency standards in New Zealand. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 22(2), 7-19. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.1997v22n2.2>
- Hedges, H. (2012). Teachers' funds of knowledge: A challenge to evidence-based practice. *Teachers and Teaching*, 18(1), 7-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2011.622548>
- Instefjord, E. J., & Munthe, E. (2017). Educating digitally competent teachers: A study of integration of professional digital competence in teacher education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 37-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.05.016>
- Kyndt, E., Gijbels, D., Grosemans, I., & Donche, V. (2016). Teachers' everyday professional development: Mapping informal learning activities, antecedents, and learning outcomes. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 1111-1150. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654315627864>
- Mahmud, S. N. D., Nasri, N. M., Samsudin, M. A., & Halim, L. (2018). Science teacher education in Malaysia: challenges and way forward. *Asia-Pacific Science Education*, 4(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41029-018-0026-3>
- Mohajan, H. K. (2020). Quantitative research: A successful investigation in natural and social sciences. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 9(4), 50-79. <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=939590>
- Orchard, J., & Winch, C. (2015). What training do teachers need?: Why theory is necessary to good teaching. *Impact*, 2015(22), 1-43. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2048-416X.2015.12002.x>

- Roberto, J., & Madrigal, D. (2018). Teacher quality in the light of the Philippine professional standards for teachers. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 1(1), 67-80.
<https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v1i1.13>
- Suwarma, I. R., & Kumano, Y. (2019). Implementation of STEM education in Indonesia: Teachers' perception of STEM integration into curriculum. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1280(5), 052052. IOP Publishing. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1280/5/052052/meta>
- Tan, A. L. (2018). Journey of science teacher education in Singapore: Past, present and future. *Asia-Pacific Science Education*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41029-017-0018-8>
- Termes, A., Edwards Jr, D. B., & Verger, A. (2020). The development and dynamics of public-private partnerships in the Philippines' education: a counterintuitive case of school choice, competition, and privatization. *Educational Policy*, 34(1), 91-117.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904819886323>
- Vera Cruz, A. C., Madden, P. E., & Asante, C. K. (2017). Toward cross-cultural curriculum development: An analysis of science education in the Philippines, Ghana, and the United States. In C. Rooffe & C. Benzina (Eds.), *Intercultural studies of curriculum: Theory, policy and practice* (pp. 37-57). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60897-6_3

Appendix

Appendix A. Seminar Training Matrix

Time Frame	Objectives	Topic	Methodology	Resources	Instructional Materials	Expected Outcomes
2 Hours	At the end of the seminar training, the participant is able to determine the techniques and instruments appropriate for teaching science course	Techniques and Instruments for Instructional Activities in Science Course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lectures • Interactive Discussion • Group Interaction 	Resource Speaker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projector • Board • Marker 	The participant was able to determine the techniques and instruments appropriate for teaching science course
2 Hours	To be able to find and know how to develop critical / creative thinking among students	Developing Critical / Creative Thinking among Science Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lectures • Interactive Discussion • Group Interaction 	Resource Speaker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projector • Board • Marker 	The participant was able to find how to develop critical / creative thinking among students

3 Hours	To be able to construct evaluation tools correctly in science course	Evaluation Tools and Test Taking Strategies in Science Course	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lectures• Interactive Discussion• Group Interaction• Seat work	Resource Speaker	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Projector• Board• Marker• Paper and Pen	The participant was able to construct evaluation tools correctly in science course
---------	--	---	---	------------------	--	--
